

A METHOD TO APPLY STRUCTURE RELEVANT IMPACT DAMAGE TO SMALL STRUCTURE RELEVANT SPECIMENS FOR DAMAGE TOLERANCE STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

An approach is presented to represent stiffened composite panels by small but "structure relevant" (SR-) specimens in compression tests to study failure mechanisms. The necessary support conditions to be applied during low velocity impact tests were determined for the SR-specimens, in order to obtain similar damage as the damage found in stiffened panels. Fractography revealed that the locations of the major delaminations in the SR-specimens due to impact were the same as in stiffened panels. These delaminations occurred where they were expected, suggesting that they can be "placed" deep inside a laminate for optimum damage tolerance. Initial compression tests on stiffened panels confirmed the high damage tolerance of the configuration considered.

INTRODUCTION

The development of structural concepts for compression loaded, *damage tolerant*, stiffened composite panels, requires an experimental investigation of the failure mechanisms that may occur, in order to improve the design, and to estimate the failure load. One of the most critical states of damage to consider is caused by low velocity impacts. The fabrication and testing of full scale stiffened panels is an expensive procedure, however, so for economic reasons most experiments are generally performed on relatively simple specimens: plain laminates with corresponding *material properties*. When testing a laminate in the form of a small specimen, supported by a frame, the damage resulting from the impact as well as the residual compression strength may deviate considerably from the experimental values that are obtained when the laminate forms part of a larger structural configuration. *Structural properties*, such as the different dynamic response during impact and the presence of multiple load paths in a larger structure, are thought to be responsible for the often superior damage tolerance observed when testing structures instead of small specimens.

At the previous ICCM-9, a small unstiffened Structure Relevant (SR-) specimen was presented [1], which is less expensive to make and test than a full scale stiffened panel, but, when combined with a support to simulate the stiffener [1-2], maintains the essential design features of the panel configuration that is being investigated, see Fig. 1. The SR-specimen was shown to be useful in providing insight in delamination spread mechanisms. (Delamination "spread" is defined as the delamination propagation under increased static loading, as opposed to delamination "growth"

under fatigue loading). In fact, tendencies of delaminations to spread along certain preferred interfaces, as observed in tests on stiffened panels, were confirmed with these SR-specimens.

In the study carried out previously [1-2], the SR-specimens were provided with artificial damage. However, a proper evaluation of the damage tolerance of different design concepts requires that genuine impact damage is applied to the SR-specimens. This impact damage must correspond to the damage resulting from impacts on the stiffened panels that are represented by the SR-specimens, hence, the impact damage must also be "structure relevant". The objective of the present study is to find a method to obtain similar impact damage in SR-specimens, at the same location and applied at the same energy level as the impact damage obtained in a number of 1-, 2-, and 3-stiffener panels. It was surmised that this can be achieved by providing appropriate support conditions for the SR-specimens to approximate the flexibility present in the larger panels. To investigate the feasibility of this approach a special frame was built to make a variety of support conditions possible. The frame was used to support both the SR-specimens and the stiffened panels during the impact tests.

Low velocity impact tests on SR-specimens were carried out with different support conditions, and the impact damage was compared with damage in the stiffened configurations, using C-scan images, fractography and impact characteristics (peak force, maximum deflection, and absorbed energy). The lay-up of the SR-specimens was selected so the results of the present study could be used to confirm the findings of the previous study [1-2] that delaminations are formed by the impact along certain preferred interfaces. If confirmed, damage tolerant panels can be designed by selecting laminate stacking sequences in such a way that the major delaminations formed within a laminate due to impact result in thick sublaminates with a high buckling resistance. Residual compression tests of two stiffened panels with impact damage were carried out to obtain a first impression of the damage tolerance of the design concept under investigation.

PANEL DESIGN AND SR-SPECIMEN CONFIGURATION

The panel design was determined with the PANOPT optimization code for stiffened panels [3], using stiffness and buckling constraints, and laminate constraints corresponding to Boeing's damage tolerant stiffened panel concept [4] with soft skin, doublers and discrete stiffeners. The design specifications, geometry and lay-up are shown in Fig. 2. The doubler lay-up is shown in Fig. 3. Delaminations are expected to occur at the interfaces near the 90-degree plies, behind the stiff, load carrying 0-degree ply stacks, as indicated in Fig. 3.

The SR-specimen based on this panel configuration is shown in Fig. 1. It has the same configuration as the skin of the stiffened panel, including the doubler build-up, but has wider skin zones at each side. The specimen is supported by frames during the impacts and during the residual compression strength tests. The supports provided by these frames consist of swiveling disks. For specimens without stiffeners, the support of the stiffener against bending was also simulated by a row of disks, as shown in Fig. 1. The frame built to support stiffened and unstiffened specimens of different sizes during the impacts is shown in Fig. 4. The stiffened panels were also supported by wooden blocks at each end, to simulate the support of ribs, reducing the deflections at these locations.

SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Unstiffened SR-specimens and stiffened specimens with one, two or three stiffeners were fabricated according to the configuration described above. All specimens were derived from a standard skin plate of the size of four SR-specimens, as shown in Fig. 5, hence, with two doublers. Two skin plates were left unstiffened, three skin plates were provided with two (pre-cured) stiffeners on top of the two doublers, and one skin plate was provided with three stiffeners, two on top of the doublers and one in between, on top of a precured doubler laminate.

The 2-stiffener panels were less stiff than the panel design of Fig. 2, with a stiffener pitch of 253 mm, and the 3-stiffener panel was stiffer than the panel design, with a stiffener pitch of only 126.5 mm. Subsequently, some of the specimens were subdivided to obtain SR-specimens and single-stiffener specimens.

The specimens were clamped between the swiveling disks of the support frame before the impact tests were carried out. Flexibility of the supports was provided by adding either 1 or 3 rubber plies with a thickness of 2 mm each to the disks. The multi-stiffener panels were supported along the longitudinal edges with 3 rubber plies, and at the lateral edges with 1 rubber ply and wooden blocks. The longitudinal edges of the 1-stiffener specimens were clamped between the disks without any rubber plies, while they were supported in the center at the stiffener tops with rubber plies. The SR-specimens were also clamped between the disks at the longitudinal edges, while the support conditions in the center were varied. The supports are shown in Fig. 6.

The complete test programme consisted of 25 impact tests, at different energy levels and at different locations on the panels. In this paper results are discussed only for impacts at the skin-stiffener transition area (see Fig. 3), considered to be the most critical location, at a kinetic energy level of 35 J. The impactor used had a mass of 2.312 kg, and a semi-spherical tup with a diameter of 1.0 inch. The impact velocity was 5.5 m/s. Tests were carried out first on the multi-stiffener panels, followed by tests on the single-stiffener panels, and on four SR-specimens to fine-tune the support conditions. Finally, impact tests with the optimum support conditions for the SR-specimens were repeated four times.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impact characteristics which are used to compare the damage in the different specimens are presented in Table 1. The force-time history was recorded during the impact tests, and from this graph the deflection under the impactor and the absorbed energy were calculated. In [5] a formula is presented to calculate the critical force needed to generate delaminations during the impact. For the laminate considered this force is 6000 N, and all impacts presented in Table 1 indeed showed peak forces higher than this force. The area within the circumference of the C-scan image, also presented in Table 1, indicates the size of the damage resulting from the impact.

Comparing the results in Table 1 for the multi-stiffener panels with dimensions of 320 x 700 mm shows that the impact on the stiffer 3-stiffener panel results in a higher peak force, a similar deflection and absorbed energy value, and a larger C-scan area than the impacts on the two more flexible 2-stiffener panels. The character of the C-scan area is the same, however. All C-scan images determined for the impact damages listed in Table 1 have the same typical "apple and clockhouse" shape as shown in Fig. 7, representing the delaminations in front (clockhouse) and behind (apple) the 90-degree ply closest to the flat side of the specimen (shown for an SR-specimen in Fig. 3). Other delaminations deeper inside the laminate are blocked off by the big apple delamination.

Post-mortem fractography of the damage in one of the 2-stiffener panels is shown at two cross sections in Fig. 8, confirming that major delaminations are formed near the two 90-degree plies, each behind one of the stacks of 0-degree plies (compare with Fig. 3). Impact test results for the two smaller single-stiffener specimens with dimensions of 243 x 340 mm compare well with the results for the larger multi-stiffener panels. The specimen with impact number 14 had only one rubber ply near the stiffener top, hence, the results are closer to the results for the 3-stiffener panel, while the specimen with impact number 13 was supported more flexibly with 3 rubber plies, and the results are closer to the 2-stiffener panels.

After these tests four impact tests were conducted on SR-specimens, each with a different flexibility of the support conditions. The specimens used for impacts 15 and 16 had 3 plies of

rubber between the center row of disks and the specimen (see Fig. 7), while the specimens with impacts 17 and 18 had only one ply. The specimens used for impacts 15 and 18 had a supporting disk positioned at the center of the specimens (also indicated in Fig. 7). The specimens used in impacts 16 and 17 had disks further away and closer to the impact site, respectively. Hence, the results of these four impacts are presented in Table 1 in the order of increasing stiffness of the support. The increased stiffness is reflected by increased peak forces and decreased deflections. The absorbed energy is not very much affected, while the resulting damage is rather random, but in size corresponds largely with the damage found in the stiffened panels.

It was concluded that the support conditions used during impact 15 generated impact damage most similar to the damage in the stiffened specimens. This conclusion was also based on fractographic images. The last four entries in Table 1 show results for SR-specimens, for which the impact conditions of impact 15 were repeated. These results are very close except for the size of the C-scan image, still within the range of the other values in Tables 1. More important is the fact that the location within the laminate of the larger delaminations (Fig. 9) is the same as that for the multi-stiffener panels (Fig. 8). These are the delaminations that are likely to propagate under increased loading.

The SR-specimens can be used to compare failure mechanisms (damage spread) rather than residual strength, which is dependent on the global structural properties of a panel. Hence, residual compression strength tests on one of the 2-stiffener panels (with impact damage 19) and on the 3-stiffener panel were carried out. The 2-stiffener panel failed at a very high axial strain level of 0.007000 with extensive postbuckling deformations, at one of the loaded panel ends and not through the impact damage. The 3-stiffener panel contained four impact damages, two in the skin between stiffeners and two underneath the stiffener edge, among which impact 12. This panel failed at a high axial strain level of 0.006200 through the two skin damages, without having reached a postbuckling state. These results indicate the superior damage tolerance of the doubler configuration of this particular panel design. Other configurations may be less damage tolerant, which will be investigated in a subsequent test programme using SR-specimens.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Support conditions for small Structure Relevant (SR-) specimens were determined, which, when applied during impact tests, result in similar damage as the impact damage that occurs in larger stiffened panels impacted at the same location and at the same energy level. These support conditions are such that the specimens are free to undergo a similar deflection during impact.

The size of the impact damage was characterised with C-scan images and the location of the damage within the laminate was characterised with fractography. The delamination size was found to show some variation under identical conditions, but the location of the major delaminations is similar for stiffened and unstiffened specimen configurations.

Two major delaminations were found adjacent to the 90-degree plies, behind the two stiff, load carrying 0-degree ply stacks, where they were expected. It is thought that by "placing" delaminations deep inside the laminate, thick sublaminates are formed by the impact with a high resistance against buckling. This will delay delamination spread and ultimate failure when the specimen is loaded by increased compression.

An initial test programme was carried out to determine the residual compression strength of two stiffened panels, and the results confirmed the high damage tolerance of the configuration considered. Further confirmation of the concept, that delaminations may be deliberately placed within a laminate by the selection of the laminate stacking sequence, will be sought in a subsequent test programme using SR-specimens with different laminate configurations.

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Table 1. Impact test results

specimen type	peak force (N)	maximum deflection (mm)	absorbed energy (J)	C-scan area (mm)	impact test number
3-st panel	8200	6.8	20	1780	12
2-st panel	7200	6.7	22	1340	10
	6650	7.3	19	1310	19
1-st panel	9000	5.7	26	1800	14
	8150	6.7	26	1340	13
SR-specimen	7800	8.8	26	1760	16
	8600	8.1	26	1260	15
	10600	6.4	27	2010	18
	12000	5.4	28	1630	17
	9300	7.2	23	1530	20
	9250	7.4	23	1350	23
	9250	7.6	23	1730	24
	9300	7.5	23	1930	25

Fig. 1 Concept of Structure Relevant specimen

Specifications: Ultimate Design Load : 2000 N/mm
 Ultimate Design Strain : 0.0055
 Global buckling loads : 2400 N/mm
 Panel length (rib pitch): 550 mm
 Shear stiffness : 20% of axial stiffness

Fig. 2 Design specifications, geometry and lay-up (dimensions in mm)

0-degree ply
 ±45-degree ply
 90-degree ply

Fig. 3 Doubler lay-up, showing preferred interfaces for delamination

Fig. 4 Support frame for impact tests

a) skin plate with saw cut plan

SR-specimen

1-stiffener panel

2-stiffener panel

3-stiffener panel

b) configurations

Fig. 5 Test specimens

a) Multi-stiffener panel

b) Single-stiffener panel

c) SR-specimen

Fig. 6 Support conditions during impact

Fig. 7 Typical C-scan image of impact damage (impact #20) with position of disk support (circle)

a) At impact site (A-A in figure 7)

b) 20 mm below impact site (B-B in figure 7)

Fig. 8 Impact damage of 2-stiffener panel (impact #10)

a) At impact site (A-A in figure 7)

b) 20 mm below impact site (B-B in figure 7)

Fig. 9 Impact damage of SR-specimen (impact #20)